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Research Article

Illustration of Jyotish, Astrology, and Shakun Shastra in Maharshi Valmiki's *Shrimad Valmiki Ramayan*

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ABSTRACT

The massive tree of the Indian knowledge system has numerous widespread and intense branches of ancient beliefs and practices. Religion, science, *Ayurveda*, palmistry, astrology, philosophy, classical dance, classical music, mathematics, medicine, surgery, *jyotish*, architecture, yoga, *vastu-shastra*, and literature are its leaves. Diverse spheres of wisdom corresponding to the above-mentioned domains are its fruits. Maharshi Valmiki was a great astrologer and a foreseer too. He was '*trikaldarshi*' as he could see past the present and the future. His knowledge of '*Jyotish vigyan*' was unparalleled. My paper focuses on the depiction of *Jyotish along with various planetary positions and their effects on human lives, as written in Shrimad Valmikiya Ramayanam*.

KEYWORDS: planets, nakshtras, punarvasu, karkat, shani

FULL PAPER

Introduction

The massive tree of the Indian knowledge system has numerous widespread and intense branches of ancient beliefs and practices. Religion, science, *Ayurveda*, palmistry, astrology, philosophy, classical dance, classical music, mathematics, medicine, surgery, *gyotish*, architecture, yoga, *vastu-shastra*, and literature are its leaves. Diverse spheres of wisdom corresponding to the above-mentioned domains are its fruits. *Maharshi Valmiki* was a great astrologer and a foreseer too. He was '*trikaldarshi*' as he could see past the present and the future. His knowledge of '*Jyotish vigyan*' was unparalleled. My paper focuses on the depiction of *Jyotish along with various planetary positions and their effects on human lives, as written in Shrimad Valmikiya Ramayanam*.

Valmiki had a deep knowledge of Indian *Jyotish Shastra*, which is reflected in his *Ramayana*, where he writes about various *nakshatras* (constellations of stars), '*tithis*', '*rashis*', '*shubh muhurat*', eclipses, and even palmistry. Valmiki in *Balkand, sarga 18, shloka 8, 9, and 10* writes:

“ततो यज्ञे समाप्ते तु ऋतूनां षट् समत्ययुः ।
ततश्च द्वादशे मासे चैत्रे नावमिके तिथौ ॥ १-१८-८
नक्षत्रेऽदितिदैवत्ये स्वोच्चसंस्थेषु पंचसु ।
ग्रहेषु कर्कटे लग्ने वाक्पताविंदुना सह ॥ १-१८-९
प्रोद्यमाने जगन्नाथं सर्वलोकनमस्कृतम् ।
कौसल्याजनयद्रामं सर्वलक्षणसंयुतम् ॥ १-१८-१०”

(Tato yagye samapte tu ritunam shatsamatyayuh,
Tatashcha dwadashemasechaitre navamike tithau.1- 18-8
Nakshatreaditidevtyai swochasanstheshu panchasu,
Griheshu karkate lagne vakpatavinduna sah 1-18-9
Prodyamane jagannatham sarvloknamaskritam,
Kaushalyajanyadramam sarvlakshansanyutam. 1-18-10)

After the holy *yagya*, Lord Rama was born on the ninth tithi of the 12th month (Chaitra as per the Hindi calendar), '*Punarvasu nakshatra*' and *karkat lagna*. At that time, all five planets were exalted. His date and time of birth, as depicted by Valmiki, were re-emphasized in the book "Dating the Era of Lord Ram", authored by Pushkar Bhatnagar. Mr Jaganandha Rama Sastri Karra used the Institute for Scientific Research on Vedas (I-SERVE) and planetarium software to determine that Lord Rama was born on 10th January 5114 BC (2,3,4) in Ayodhya. As per the Indian calendar, the time of the birth is between 12 noon and 1:00 p.m. '*Shukla paksh*' in the *Chaitra* month."

Mr Sastri also used the Swiss Ephemeris available on the Astro Data Bank website and extracted the data files. In his paper entitled "Possibility for Existence of Astrological Planetary Positions as per Sage Valmiki-Research analysis", he writes:

"Based on my data extracts from the data files obtained from the Astro dentist website, and cross-referencing with JHoraver 8 software. I can confirm that on the above day in 7875 ADS, the astrological planetary positions mentioned by Sage Valmiki are possible. This guarantees that on this day the astrological planetary combinations mentioned by sage Valmiki really exist, irrespective of the correlation of this unique combination with the mythological story".

The Indian knowledge system has its roots deeply embedded in the wisdom evolved over centuries of research and hard work. Valmiki Ji, in his Shrimad Ramayanam, writes about various yogas. In Shri Ram's horoscope, we find 'Dharma Karmadhipati Yoga', 'Gajkesari Yoga', and 'Mahalaxmi Yoga'. Sanjay Rath in his book *CruX of Vedic astrology: Timing of Events* very aptly writes: "Rama was born in Cancer lagna....for a cancer ascendant, Jupiter rules the sixth and 9th houses and a relationship between Jupiter and Mars can bring the highest yoga called *Dharma Karmadhipathi Yoga* which ensures a lot of power, status, fame and fortune as the fifth 10th and 9th houses are involved. Jaimini provides additional yardsticks (such as placements) for a more detailed prediction. If this yoga is in the first/seventh house, it fructifies in later life, and that too after enduring a lot of hardship and struggle. We find this in the horoscope of Bhagwan Shri Ramchandra (Chart 2), where Jupiter and Moon conjoin in Cancer ascendant, resulting in *Gajkesari and Mahalaxmi Yoga*. Jaimini (*upadesha sutras*) gives this as a combination of undying fame, and Shri Ram is adored and idolized by the Hindus as the *Dharma Avatar*. The *Dharma Karmadhipati yoga* is along the ascendant and seventh house and indicates suffering and hardship before the beginning of the *Rajyoga*. Shri Ram was exiled for 14 years, which were spent in the wild jungles, when his wife was abducted. Aided by the apes (Mars exalted in the seventh house is the cause of the destruction of foes) and Shri Hanuman, he was able to defeat the Lanka King Ravana and retrieve his wife."

Venus	Sun	Mercury	
	Chart No. 2 Shri. Ram		Lagna Moon Jupiter
Mars		Saturn Rahu	

Swami Karpatriji Maharaj, in his book *Ramayan Mimansa*, writes that according to astrologers, Ravi (sun), Bhauma (Mars), Guru (Jupiter), Shukra (Venus), and *Shani* (Saturn) were all exalted. The Sun was in Aries, Mars in Capricorn, Jupiter in Cancer, Venus in Pisces, and Saturn in Libra. Roughly speaking, the *Saptrishi* stay in a sign for about a thousand years, *Varuna* for 14 years, and *Shani* for about 2.5 years. The sun stays in a sign for one month, and Jupiter for one year. Considering the Sun, Jupiter, and Saturn and calculating the five exalted planets, the birth time of Ramchandra was 1,85,071 years ago. According to these planetary positions, the greatness of Ram Rajya and Rama's extraordinary strength, prosperity, and glory were incomparable. As Mars was exalted, it was not auspicious; hence, there were troubles related to women, etc. However, according to Puranic evidence, the twenty-fourth Treta Yuga was the time of Rama. It is appropriate to consider, based on that, the planetary positions described in Valmiki Ramayana must have also existed at that time". (Page 677)

Valmiki also described good and bad omens, 'muhurt vichar' (before starting any journey), and various *nakshatras* and their effects on human lives in his Ramayana. King Dashrath called Ram and expressed his anguish and tension over the bad dreams he was having those days. He also told him that his birth nakshatra was suffering from the bad condition created by the position of 'Surya', 'Mangal', and 'Rahu'. He also expresses his anxiety that such planetary positions can be harmful to a king; they can even lead to his death. Then he tells him that at that time the moon was in '*punarvasu nakshatra*' and was about to enter into '*Pushya nakshatra*'. '*Pushya nakshatra*' is the best one for the coronation of a king; therefore, you should get your coronation done during '*Pushya nakshatra*.'

{“ *Api chadyashubhan Ram swapnan pashyami Raghav ,
Sanirghata divolkashcha patanti hi mahasvanah.
Avashtabdham cha me Ram Nakshtram Darungrahai,
Avedyanti Devagyah suryangkrahubhih.
Prayen cha nimittanamidrashanam samudbhave,
Raja hi mrityumvapnoti ghoram chapadmrichati...*”

(Valmiki Ramayan 2/4/17-19)

*“Adyah chandroabhyupgamat pushyat purvam punarvasum,
Shvah pushyayogam niyatam vakshyante daivochintakah.”*

(Valmiki Ramayan 2/4/210) Sanskrit Version}

Trishanku, Mars, Jupiter, Mercury, and all other planets, along with Venus and Saturn, reached near the Moon at night with ‘Vakra’ motion and became situated with a fierce aura. The radiance of the constellations faded. The planets became dim. They all appeared smoky, situated in the opposite direction in the sky. The cloud formations spread across the sky, resembling a surging ocean due to the wind's force. An earthquake struck the city. All directions became distressed, and darkness spread over them. At that time, neither any planet nor constellation remained shining:

{ *“Trishankurlohitangascha brihaspatibudhavapi,
Daruna somambhyetya griha sarve vyavasthitah.
Nakshatrani gatarchinshi grihashcha gattejsah,
Vishakhascha sadhumascha nabhasi prachakashire.
Kalikanilvegen mahodadhirivoothitah,
Rame vanam pravrajite nagram prachchal tat.
Disah paryakulah sarvastimirenev samvritah,
Na griho napi nakshatram prachakashe na kinchan.”*

Valmiki Ramayan 2/41/11-14}

Vibhishana describes various ominous signs that occurred in Lanka. Trijata’s bad dream predicts the forthcoming disaster and destruction of Ravana's dynasty. She says that:

“All the sons of Ravana, too, were seen by me with shaven heads and bathed in oil. Nay, Ravana, the ten-headed monster, departed in a southern direction on the back of a boar, his eldest son, Meghanada (the conqueror of Indra), too, on the back of a dolphin, and Kumbhakarna on the back of a camel. In that dream, Vibhishana, Ravana’s youngest brother, alone was seen by me, shaded with a white canopy, dressed in white and wearing a white garland, nay, smeared with white sandal-paste. Hailed with blasts of conch-shells and the beating of kettledrums as well as with dances and songs, Vibhishana stood there in the air mounted on a four-tusked celestial elephant closely resembling a hill and trumpeting like thunder, with four ministers. (31 to 35)” (Srimad Valmiki-Ramayana with Sanskrit text and Translation into English)

{ *Ravanasya sutah sarve mundastailsamukshitah,
Varahen dashgrivahsishumaren chendrajit.
Ushtren kumbhkarnascha prayato dakshinam disham,
Ekstatra maya drashtah Shweta chhatron vibhishanah.*

*Shukla malyamber dhara shuklagandhaanulepanah,
Shankh dundubhi nirghoshenritya geetairlankatah.
Aaruhya shaail sankasham meghasthNitani swanam,
chaturdantham gajam divyamaste tatra vibhishanh.
Chaturbhiih sachivoe sardham vauhaysamupsthitah.
(Valmiki Ramayan 5/27/31-34)*

Valmiki also describes the 'shubh shakunas' or the good omens that make goddess Sita happy and distress-free. His knowledge of *shakun shastra* and *gyotish shastra* was profound. His depiction of 'janam nakshatras', various eclipses (In *Ayodhya kand*, 12th Sarga: Bharata's face has been compared with eclipsed moon, again in the same *Kand*, 18th Sarga shloka no.6 he refers to the solar eclipse), various *muhurtas* like: 'Dhruv', 'Saumya', (*Ayodhyakand*, 56th Sarga), 'Maitra'(in 89th Sarga), 'Vijay' (in 73rd Sarga), frequent occurrence of various *nakshatas* like 'Pushya', 'Falguni', 'Punarvasu', etc. reflect his deep understanding of Indian *Jyotish Shatra*. Sri Mad Ramayanam is indubitably a vast sea of human knowledge, with priceless gems hidden at its depths.

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